

MOLECULAR MODELING OF A BISMALEIMIDE RESIN

TREVOR WAVRUNEK

MICHIGAN TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

ADVISOR: DR. GREGORY ODEGARD

CMMR Lab™

MOTIVATION: NEXT GENERATION COMPOSITES

- Polymer-CF composites are dominant materials for high specific strength & stiffness applications
- Significant potential improvement in specific properties with polymer nanocomposites
- Multiscale simulation can significantly cut down on material design costs (ICME)

Rocket Lab Electron (2023)

ROLE OF MOLECULAR SIMULATION

I: Chemistry

O: Performance

- MD directly informs residual stress buildup and cracking from chemical and thermal factors
- Experimental methods to obtain mid-cure properties are difficult or nonexistent

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS

- **Premise:**

Atoms' dynamic behavior can be modeled using classical physics.

- Numerical, iterative solution of a dynamical physics problem using classical equations of motion:

$$m_i \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_i = \mathbf{f}_i = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{r}_i} E_{pot}$$

$$E_{pot} = E_{bond} + E_{angle} + E_{torsion} + E_{nonbond}$$

- Energies are calculated with the help of (usually) empirical forcefields

PROJECT GOAL

Predict the thermomechanical property evolution and polymer structure of a 3-component HP Bismaleimide resin as a function of degree of cure for use in a multi-scale model.

Virtual
Polymerization

Simulated Tests

Degree of Cure
Process Insights

BISMALEIMIDE RESIN

- High-performance variant based on a classic 2-component system
 - Easily processable
 - Good adhesion to fibers
 - Great thermal properties
- Utilizes 2-stage cure:
 1. “Initial Cure”
 2. “Post Cure”

o,o'-diallylbisphenol A
(DABPA)

4,4'-Bismaleimidodiphenylmethane
(BMPM)

THEORIZED BMI CHEMISTRY

Morgan, R. J. et al. *Polymer* **38**, 639–646 (1997).

Evsyukov, S. E. & Pohlmann, T. *Current Trends in Polymer Science* **20**, (2020).

Phelan, J. C. & Sung, C. S. P. *Macromolecules* **30**, 6837–6844 (1997).

Rozenberg, B. A., et al. *Polym. for Adv. Technologies* **13**, 837–844 (2002).

Mijović, J. & Andjelić, S. *Macromolecules* **29**, 239–246 (1996).

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS WORKFLOW

Build un-crosslinked system of monomers (LUNAR), densify to liquid (1.2g/cc) in LAMMPS

Crosslink using combination of proposed reactions (REACTER)

Cool and relax system to 300K & 1.0 atm

Deform and measure energy, pressure, & geometry changes

Use these to estimate thermomechanical properties (G , E , K , ν , σ , T_g , & CTE)

Simulation Construction

Property Prediction

SIMULATION PARAMETERS

- x5 replicates, 15k atoms
- 2-stage polymerization with ramps
 - NVT, $\rho=1.2$ g/cc during production
 - Temperature +100K from resin datasheet
- Mechanical testing at $1e8$ s⁻¹
 - RFR analysis, no PCFF-2xe
- Annealing simulation
 - 50 K/ns heating rate
 - Hyperbola fit + bilinear regression used

KINETIC AND GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS

- Arrhenius Equation

$$p(\text{reaction}) = Ae^{-\frac{E_a}{R(T+T')}}$$

- Pre-exponential taken as order of magnitude
- Non-constrained pre-exponential (A) and E_a tuned to match experimental data

Reaction	A (mol-s) ⁻¹	E _a (kcal/mol)	Source
Ene	1e6	16.9	[1]
Radical from Maleimide	parametric	21.9	[1]
Radical from Ene	parametric	18.0	-
Etherification	parametric	10	-

EFFECT OF PRE-EXPONENTIAL (A)

GEL POINT DETERMINATION

Replicate	Gel Point
1	38.2
2	38.6
3	43
4	37.6
5	38.2
Average	39.1 ± 2.2

SHRINKAGE AT PROCESS TEMPERATURE

- Shrinkage within range of expected values
 - Pure BMPM: **0.7%**
 - Matrimid 5292: **5.2%**
 - This study: **1.81%**
- Room Temp. density is close to spec.
 - MD: **1.259 g/cc**
 - Spec: **1.250 g/cc**

MECHANICAL PROPERTY PREDICTION

MECHANICAL RESULTS

● DIC Data ■ MD Data ■ Shear Modulus (Calculated)

THERMAL RESULTS

SUMMARY

- Implementation of competing reaction kinetics was incorporated into a process model for an engineering BMI thermoset
- Cure kinetics, as well as physical and mechanical properties are compliant, although T_G is overpredicted
- Higher fidelity ICME could inform improved resin cure processes and manufacturing design of thermoset matrix composites

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